

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS ENHANCEMENT IN CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES VIA ASYMMETRIC FLAX FIBER HYBRIDIZATION

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ABSTRACT

The brittle nature of the carbon fiber reinforced composites (CFRP) makes them susceptible to interlaminar fracture failures due to poor fracture toughness. This work explores the use of natural flax fiber and cellulose nanofibers to enhance the mode-I and mode-II fracture toughness of CFRP. The first part investigates the effect of asymmetric distribution of woven flax fiber in a hybrid arrangement with woven carbon fiber on the mode-I fracture toughness in comparison to CFRP. For this purpose, four different hybrid stacking sequences along with CFRP were tested using the double cantilever beam test. The critical energy release rate (G_C) evaluated exhibited a 70% increase for a one-interface carbon/flax hybrid layup. However, increasing the number of carbon/flax layers from one to four resulted in a decrease in G_C , highlighting the importance of ply placement in a hybrid arrangement for improved toughness. The experimentally evaluated G_C was used as an input in a numerical solver, which predicted the experimental response accurately. Due to the decrease in shear strength of the hybrid composite, the mode-II fracture toughness was complemented by adding cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) at the crack interface of CFRP and hybrid carbon/flax fiber reinforced composite. The CNFs were sprayed at 0.5, 0.1, and 0.2 wt% on the interface layers, resulting in an 18% and 20% increase in the mode-II fracture toughness for the CFRP and hybrid carbon/flax fiber reinforced composites, respectively. The shear strength and stiffness of the modified crack interfaces were evaluated using the cohesive zone numerical model, which showed close compliance with the experimental load-displacement plots. The fracture morphology using SEM and 3D optical microscope revealed the anchoring role of CNFs in deviating the crack path, resulting in the crack softening effect. Overall, the potential of natural fibers has been highlighted to design high-performance, lightweight, and sustainable composite structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber-reinforced composites are widely used in the automotive and aerospace sectors due to their high specific strength and stiffness, enabling lightweight and fuel-efficient designs [1]. However, their brittleness and high cost limit broader application, as failures often lead to costly part replacements. To address this, hybridization with cheaper fibers like glass has been adopted, especially in interlaminar configurations where fibers are stacked layer by layer. This approach combines the strengths of different fibers while minimizing their weaknesses. Carbon/glass hybrids reduce brittleness and cost, making them popular in many applications [2]. However, growing demand for sustainable and recyclable materials calls for eco-friendly alternatives to synthetic fibers without compromising structural integrity.

Natural fibers like flax offer a promising alternative for hybridization with high-performance carbon fibers, as their specific stiffness is comparable to that of glass fibers. In hybrid composites, flax can serve as the ductile component, enhancing toughness when combined with brittle carbon fibers [3]. A common issue with CFRPs is low-velocity impact damage, which often occurs beneath the surface and remains undetectable visually. These internal damages typically develop at the fiber-matrix interface or the

interface between plies in interlaminar hybrid composites. To assess such failures, interlaminar fracture toughness tests under mode-I (opening) and mode-II (sliding) are widely employed to evaluate the toughness of composites [4].

Studies on mode-I fracture toughness for hybrid natural and synthetic fiber hybrid composites are limited in terms of taking the relevant stiffness of the beams of the double cantilever beam specimens and the utilization of asymmetric distribution of the plies to see the fracture at the natural and synthetic ply interface [5]. Moreover, the hybridization of weak natural fibers with strong carbon fibers results in a reduced shear strength, resulting in a reduction in mode-II fracture of the hybrid. For this reason, eco-friendly nano-species like cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) are adopted to offset the decrement in shear strength. But loading the CNFs at the interface so far has been in the form of interleaves that require time and extra processing steps for preparing composites with enhanced fracture toughness [6].

This work explores the effect of asymmetric hybrid placement of carbon/flax fiber composites on the mode-I fracture toughness compared to an all-carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite. Moreover, the effect of CNFs on the mode-II fracture toughness of CFRP and hybrid carbon/flax has been studied and compared with CFRP with a simple deposition method of CNFs on the interface layer. This is done to complement the decrease in shear strength due to the hybridization of flax with carbon fiber. The experimental load-displacement response has been replicated using numerical analysis, both for mode-I and mode-II fracture toughness tests. The fracture morphology of the cracked surface was observed under 3D optical microscopy and scanning electron micrographs (SEM).

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

Plain woven CF3327-3K carbon fiber fabric was acquired from Hankuk Carbon Co., South Korea. 2-2 and Twill woven flax fiber fabric (FLAXDRYTM BL200) was supplied by EcoTechnilin, France was used as reinforcements, and Vinyl ester resin, along with cobalt naphthenate (accelerator) and methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (hardener), was supplied by CCP Composites, South Korea. was used as a matrix. The laminates were prepared by a conventional vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. A Teflon insert was used to introduce a pre-crack for the mode-I and mode-II test samples. The cellulose nanofibers were extracted from *Imperata cylindrica* grass using a hybrid chemical and mechanical treatment [7].

2.2 Experimental

The testing and specimen preparation for mode-I fracture toughness were performed as per ASTM D5528 standard using the modified beam theory. A material testing system (MTS) in a tensile mode at 3 mm/min was used to conduct the test. A double cantilever beam (DCB) test specimen was prepared, and hinges were attached using an epoxy adhesive film (Loctite EA 9695, Henkel, Korea). For the mode-II fracture toughness test, the ASTM D7905 standard was used to prepare the end-notched flexural test specimen and conduct the test. The universal testing machine (UTM) was used in a 3-point bending mode and 0.5 mm/min loading rate.

2.3 Numerical analysis

The numerical analysis was performed using ANSYS Workbench 2023 R2. For mode-I fracture toughness, a virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) was employed where the experimental G_C value was used as an input in the numerical model to simulate the experimental load-displacement behavior. For mode-II fracture toughness, a fracture energy-based cohesive zone model under pure mode-II was employed to identify the tangential contact stress (τ_{max}) and tangential contact stiffness (kt). The experimentally calculated mode-II toughness (G_{IIC}) was used directly as the critical fracture energy for tangential slip. Table 1 lists the engineering data used for the numerical analysis. A representative volume element (RVE) analysis was performed to extract the engineering data for CFRP and flax fiber reinforced polymer (FFRP).

Engineering Constants	CFRP	FFRP
ρ (g/cm ³)	1.5	1.3
$E_x = E_y$ (GPa)	41	10
E_z (GPa)	10	6
$\nu_{yz} = \nu_{xz}$	0.5	0.4
ν_{xy}	0.3	0.1
$G_{yz} = G_{xz}$ (GPa)	3.4	2
G_{xy} (GPa)	5	2

Table 1: Engineering Data

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Mode-I fracture toughness

Fig. 1 discusses the mode-I fracture toughness test. Fig. 1(a) shows the comparison of load displacement response for pure and hybrid laminates. As shown in the figure, the CFRP laminate with a peak load of 44N has the lowest load point displacement, signifying the brittle fracture. The FFRP with a peak load of 30N has a higher load point displacement, indicating its ductile nature. The hybrid laminates show a response between these two. The one interface hybrid (F/C)3/F//C/(F/C)3 exhibits the highest peak load of 50N along with the load point displacement. The peak load and the load point displacement decrease as the number of carbon/flax plies increases from one to four, showing the effect of ply asymmetry and concurrently the distribution of plies in the hybrid arrangement. The two-interface hybrid (F3C2F2//C2F2C3) exhibits a peak load at around 42N, which is like the CFRP but has higher load point displacement. For the three-interface (F2C2F3//C3F3C2), the peak load drops to 32N, which is almost like FFRP in terms of load point displacement, also. The four-interface hybrid F3C4//F4C3 exhibits similar values but lower load point displacement relevant to FFRP. Consequently, to the load displacement behaviour, Fig. 1(b) shows the critical fracture energy (G_c), which exhibits the highest value 910 J/m² for the one interface (F/C)3/F//C/(F/C)3 hybrid compared to 440 J/m² for CFRP. This is a significant improvement of 70% for the mode-I fracture toughness via hybridization. The two-interface hybrid (F3C2F2//C2F2C3) exhibits a value of 749 J/m², followed by the three-interface (F2C2F3//C3F3C2) hybrid at 656 J/m² and the four-interface hybrid F3C4//F4C3 at 430 J/m². The FFRP exhibits G_{IC} equivalent to 600 J/m² more than CFRP due to the higher load point displacement. These results indicate at the fact that a more equal asymmetric distribution of the flax plies in the beams of the DCB test specimen results in lower stiffness, causing the beams to deform more, which becomes stiff when the plies start to be grouped in other asymmetric hybrid arrangements mentioned. Fig. 1(c) shows the load displacement curves comparison of the numerical simulation model and experimental results. As exhibited, the numerical curves show close compliance in terms of predicting the peak load and the load point displacement for all the laminates, which is critical in estimating the initiation critical mode-I fracture toughness. The fracture morphology exhibited for the one interface hybrid in Fig. 1(d) shows the top view of the fractured beams, with (1) being the bottom being showing 3D optical microscopic images of the carbon ply with resin-rich region near the crack initiation point and the filament pullout indication at fiber bridging. The (2) shows the top beams' fractured surface, where the flax ply is visible underneath the resin layer on top. The texture of the opposing CFRP ply has visibly imprinted itself on the flax ply, showing mechanical interlocking effects. The SEM images taken from the side of the top flax ply show a thick resin layer on the surface of the flax ply. This shows the hydrophilicity of natural fibers, causing the resin layer to accumulate on the flax ply surface [8]. In composites, it's not an ideal

scenario as hydrophilicity leads to weak interfacial strength between the fiber and matrix, but in this case, it leads to a mechanical interlocking effect between the two different interfaces, resulting in a significant increase in the mode-I fracture toughness.

Figure 1: Mode-I fracture toughness, (a) Load displacement curves, (b) Critical fracture toughness, (c) Load displacement curves comparison, (d) fracture morphology.

3.2 Mode-II fracture toughness

Fig. 2 discusses the mode-II fracture toughness test. Fig. 1(a) shows the load displacement response of CFRP, CFRP_{CNFs}, hybrid, and hybrid with CNFs. From the load displacement curves, the CFRP, after reaching its peak load at around 680N, undergoes a sudden drop, which indicates the brittle fracture. The CFRP with 0.05% CNFs exhibits a peak load at around 670N, but due to the presence of CNFs, the load point displacement showed an increase compared to the CFRP. After attaining the peak load, there is no sudden drop, demonstrating the effect the CNFs have. This behaviour becomes more dominant for the CFRP with 0.1% CNFs, where the peak load reaches approximately 700N, and the crack arrest at the peak load is also more visible before the load drop. By increasing the CNFs to 0.2% the peak load reduces to around 580N, indicating the ability of the CNFs to act as an impurity at higher loading percentages, causing the crack to initiate much earlier. The reason for this behaviour is the inherent nature of the cellulose, which is derived from a natural resource, tends to be hydrophilic, resulting in reaction with matrix materials and causing the weakening of hydrogen bonding within itself. This causes a weak interfacial adhesion with the matrix, hence acting as an impurity at higher weight percentages. Similar behaviour is observed for hybrid layups [9]. In the hybrid with only flax fabric at the interface (C7/F//C7) the lowest peak load is observed at 475N, and despite no sudden load drop, the effect of placing flax fabric only at the interface was not effective. Adding 0.5 wt% of CNFs on the flax fabric at the interface (C7/F0.05% CNFs//C7) improves not only the peak load up to 500N but also enhances the crack arrest behaviour evident from the shape of the curve post peak load. A similar effect is observed for 0.1 wt% of CNFs at the hybrid interface (C7/F0.1% CNFs//C7) with a peak load at 528N, but the crack arrest post maximum load is not as dominant as the hybrid with 0.05 wt% of CNFs. Corresponding to this behaviour the G_{IIC} values are given in Fig. 2(b). The CFRP showed a G_{IIC} value of 1056 J/m^2 , compared to 1045 J/m^2 for CFRP with 0.05% CNFs and 1270 J/m^2 for CFRP with 0.1% of CNFs. This shows an increase of 18% in the G_{IIC} value of CFRP with 0.1% of CNFs compared to pure CFRP. For the hybrid without CNFs, the G_{IIC} is 1006 J/m^2 which shows the decrease in shear strength of the hybrid composite. With CNFs at 0.05 wt%, the hybrid composite exhibits the highest G_{IIC} , i.e., 1295 J/m^2 , while

the hybrid with 0.1 wt% of CNFs showed almost similar G_{IIC} compared to CFRP. Fig. 2(c) shows the comparison between numerical and experimental results. As shown, the cohesive zone numerical model shows close compliance to the experimental load-displacement response. In terms of the peak load, load point displacement, and the post-crack behaviour, all the attributes are correctly predicted by the numerical model for all the layups. Fig. 4(d) shows the fracture morphology under SEM for CFRP with 0.1% of CNFs and the hybrid with 0.05% CNFs. As visible from the images, the crack initiation sites showed agglomerated CNFs and fibers being pulled out from the opposing surface. This shows the anchoring role the CNFs play when loaded at their optimum amount can deviate the crack path, causing crack softening behaviour discussed from the load displacement curves. Moreover, the elongation of the crack is also due to increased fiber bridging, causing an increase in the mode-II fracture toughness.

Figure 2: Mode-II fracture toughness, (a) Load displacement curves, (b) Critical fracture toughness, (c) Load displacement curves comparison, (d) fracture morphology.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the interlaminar fracture toughness of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites was significantly enhanced through two strategies: interlaminar hybridization with flax fibers for mode I and the incorporation of cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) for mode II. Under Mode-I loading, an asymmetric stacking sequence of flax and carbon fiber ((F/C)₃/F//C/(F/C)₃) demonstrated a 70% increase in critical energy release rate (G_{IC}) compared to conventional CFRP. For mode-II, CNFs were deposited both directly at the crack interface and via CNF-loaded flax fabrics. An 18% increase in G_{IIC} was observed for CFRP with 0.1 wt% CNFs, and a 20% increase for the hybrid with 0.05 wt% CNFs-loaded flax interface, indicating improved crack resistance during delamination. However, 0.2 wt% CNFs reduced performance due to excessive nanofiber content, resulting in impurities at the crack interface. Numerical simulations using the virtual crack closure technique for mode-I and the cohesive zone method for mode-II effectively replicated the fracture behavior, identifying the peak loads, load point displacements, and post-crack behavior. SEM and 3D microscopy confirmed increased fiber bridging due to mechanical interlocking in the case of mode-I fracture. In case of mode-II, crack deflection and matrix plasticity due to the presence of CNFs, contributing to a more stable delamination as opposed to pure CFRP and hybrid without CNFs. Overall, the study underscores the importance of ply architecture and nanofiber optimization for enhancing fracture toughness in CFRP composites.

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